

Services to Create a Research Data Management Container (RDMC)

A workflow to enhance research data and software management

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Abstract

The Research Data Management Container (RDMC) is a concept for preserving research data, research software, and their context [1] [2]. Its Reusable Execution Environment (REE) [3] facilitates the running of software with the necessary data in a pre-defined separate environment. This separation has the advantage of preventing any interaction between the preserved data and the software and the running the software that might alter the dataset. The roadmap proposed at the previous CoRDI conference outlined three phases: first, implementation of a prototype RDMC; second, creation of a secure environment with user-dependent access; and finally, construction of a platform for the management of RDMCs [4]. This results in three major processes: 1. constructing the RDMC, 2. opening the RDMC, and 3. technical management of RDMCs. This presentation focuses on the first process.

In addition to the fact that there could be multiple approaches to constructing the RDMC, we decided to create a workflow to guide users through the creation process [5]. By implementing this creation workflow, it became evident that the process needed to be split into different reusable services. Figure 1 illustrates the various services necessary to construct, seal, and publish the container.

Figure 1. RDMC Creation Workflow in Context of necessary services

The services have the following purposes:

- **RDMC Creator** is the workflow to create the RDMC. This creator guides the user through the steps to add artifacts to the RDMC, annotates necessary metadata, and handles connections to the other services.
- **Single Sign-On (SSO)** is the service to identify users in an identity management system. Currently, the academic cloud is used, which is also within the scope of IAM4NFDI.
- **REE Creator** is a service that records the build process of a project's Docker image.
- **Sealing Service** converts the content into an immutable container to allow detection of unintentional or malicious manipulation of its contents [5].
- **Research Data/Software Repository** is a platform to publish artifacts, such as Zenodo or Dataverse. In these platforms, the RDMC can be published, receive a persistent identifier, and be archived without further guarantees¹.
- **Artifact Evaluation Platform** is a platform that can be used for an evaluation track at a conference. For some user stories, there is an export from the RDMC to a HotCRP instance.

The National Research Data Infrastructure for and with Computer Science (NFDIxCS) services are still under development, but links to try out their current status are available in the Resources section. Currently, the connection to the creation workflow is implemented through direct service Application Programming Interface (API) calls. From an architectural perspective, this should be moved to a centralized NFDI API infrastructure, which would provide both a more convenient user/developer experience and a platform for publishing NFDI-developed services through this API.

Resources

- RDMC Creation Workflow Demo. <https://rdmc.create.nfdixcs.org/> "A demonstrator to show how to use the creation workflow without creating an actual RDMC."
- RDMC Creation Workflow Prototype. [Software Heritage Archive](#) "This workflow supports to create a RDMC locally."
- REE Creator. <https://ree.create.nfdixcs.org/> "Service which creates recordings based on the project's Docker image by recording the build process and gives the opportunity to replay the recording later."
- Artifact Evaluation Platform. <https://ae.nfdixcs.org/> "A platform to support artifact evaluations in corresponding tracks in conferences by providing a review mechanism based on Hot Conference Review Process (HotCRP). This platform allows handling submissions and reviews, decision making, and anonymous communication between authors and reviewers."

Author contributions

Jan Bernoth: Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing - Original Draft, Writing – review & editing.

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Michael Goedicke Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

¹Of course, the guarantees are those provided by the operators of the related repository platforms. When NFDIxCS provides such a repository, it will explicitly publish information regarding the guarantees provided.

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